

Analytical Applications of 1-Amidino-2-thiourea. Part V. Gravimetric Determination of Selenium

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A new gravimetric method has been developed for the determination of selenium, based on the quantitative reduction of selenites and selenates to elementary selenium by amidinothiourea (ATU) in hydrochloric acid solutions. In the range of 43.5 to 347.8 mg. of selenium in 100 ml solution, the accuracy and the standard deviation of the method are 0.2% and 0.24% respectively. Under the experimental conditions employed, anions and cations do not interfere. Binary mixtures containing selenium have been analysed by this method.

Recent use of selenium in various commercial and industrial products has emphasized the need of a rapid and accurate method for the estimation of selenium. The classical method¹ for the estimation of selenium by reduction of selenites to elementary selenium, using SO_2 as a reducing agent, is laborious and time consuming. Other reducing agents, such as Sn(II) , Ti(III) , hydrazine, hypophosphite², and thiourea³, have been used. But these methods suffer from interference of ions such as Au(III) , Hg(II) , or nitrate. Recently reported gravimetric determination of selenium with 2,3-diaminonaphthalene by Lott *et al.*⁴ is the first instance where selenium is estimated as an organic complex. This method, however, requires critical control of acid concentration, temperature, and time of precipitations. Further, Ce(III) and Ti(III) interfere and Cd(II) and Fe(III) have a tendency to coprecipitate with selenium. It has a relative standard deviation of 1.52%.

1-Amidino-2-thiourea (ATU), $\text{H}_2\text{N-C(=NH)-NH-C(=S)-NH}_2$, reduces selenites and selenates in HCl solution to elementary selenium. This reagent, which has already been used for gravimetric determination of silver⁵, nickel⁶, mercury⁷, and spectrophotometric determination of silver⁸, has been employed in estimating selenium.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Solutions of selenium were prepared by dissolving SeO_2 in double distilled water and the strength of the solution was determined by SO_2 method¹.

*Presented before Inorganic and Physical Chemistry Section of the First Annual Convention of Chemists, held under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society, in Bombay in December 1963.

1. Keller, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, 19, 771.
2. Evans, *Analyst*, 1942, 67, 346.
3. Murthy and Chandrasekhariah, *Curr. Sci.*, 1961, 9, 336.
4. *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, 35, 1159.
5. Nadkarni and Haldar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 427.
6. *Idem*, *Proc. Science Congress*, 1964.
7. *Idem*, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 319.
8. *Idem*, *ibid.* (in press).

Interference due to a number of cations and anions was studied by addition of solutions of appropriate salts. The concentrations of the cations and the anions present in the test solution were determined by standard procedures⁹.

1-Amidino-2-thiourea was prepared as described earlier⁵. A 2% aqueous solution of the reagent was employed for the precipitation of selenium.

Determination of Selenium.—To a solution of selenite in HCl amidinothiourea was added in excess. The acidity of the solution was so adjusted that the final solution was at least 3.5*N* with respect to HCl. Red precipitates of selenium appeared immediately. The solution was centrifuged and filtered through a weighed, sintered-bed crucible. The precipitate was washed with cold water, followed by hot water; it was dried at 110° and weighed as metallic selenium.

Selenate may be reduced to selenite by heating with HCl and then the above procedure may be followed.

TABLE I

Effect of HCl concentration, time of precipitation, and temperature on the precipitation of selenium.

Normality of HCl.	Time allowed for pptn.	Temp. of pptn.	Amount of Se.		%Error.	Remarks.
			Present.	Found.		
3.0 <i>N</i>	4 hr.	Room temp.	108.70 mg.	107.85 mg.	-0.70	Very slow pptn.
3.5	"	"	"	108.67	-0.03	Slow pptn.
4.0	"	"	"	108.73	+0.03	Rapid pptn.
5.0	"	"	"	108.61	-0.08	"
6.0	"	"	"	108.79	+0.08	Immediate pptn.
8.0	"	"	"	108.82	+0.10	"
5.0	15 min.	"	122.2	41.50	..	Incomplete pptn.
"	1 hr.	"	"	108.00	..	"
"	2	"	"	112.20	-8.00	"
"	4	"	"	122.10	-0.08	Complete pptn.
"	12	"	"	122.20	+0.10	"
"	15 min.	40°	144.20	137.10	..	Incomplete pptn.
"	30 "	"	"	144.20	±0.00	..
"	1 hr.	"	"	142.70	-1.04	Low results
"	2	"	"	141.70	-1.70	"

TABLE II

Estimation of selenium with amidinothiourea.

Sr. No.	Amount of selenium.			Sr. No.	Amount of selenium.		
	Present.	Found.	%Error.		Present.	Found.	%Error.
1	7.21 mg.	7.10 mg.	-1.5	6	108.75 mg.	108.79 mg.	+0.03
2	14.42	14.60	+1.2	7	152.18	152.29	+0.08
3	24.40	24.50	+0.4	8	217.40	217.10	-0.1
4	43.50	43.41	-0.2	9	304.36	304.72	+0.11
5	73.20	73.40	+0.2	10	347.84	348.13	+0.08

9. Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green and Co. Ltd., London, 1963.

TABLE III

Analysis of binary mixtures.

Selenium present = 148.6 mg.

Complexing agent added.	So found.	%Error.	Cations.	Amount of cation.		%Error
				Added.	Found.	
Citric acid	148.3 mg.	-0.20	Cu(II)	1195.6 mg.	1199.0 mg.	+0.28
"	148.4	-0.13	Hg(II)	447.6	447.3	-0.06
"	148.8	+0.13	Ag(I)	307.2	307.6	+0.13
"	148.0	+0.20	Te(IV)	297.6	297.7	+0.04
Tartaric acid	148.0	± 0.00	Te(VI)	238.1	237.5	-0.25
Molybdate (II)	148.3	-0.20	Te(VI)	446.4	447.6	+0.26

DISCUSSION

For complete precipitation of selenium, concentration of HCl should be at least 3.5-4.0N. At lower acidities, the reaction is very slow and incomplete, as can be seen in Table I. Except in highly acidic solutions, selenites and selenates are not affected by amidinothiourea at the room temperature; a slight reduction, however, takes place on boiling the alkaline solution. At least four hours are required for quantitative precipitation of selenium at the room temperature. Heating the solution at 40° reduces the time for complete precipitation to 30 min., but duration of heating needs to be carefully controlled, as evident from the results in Table I. It has been observed that complete precipitation of selenium can be achieved within a very short time if precipitation is carried out in a 50-ml centrifuge cone and the solution is centrifuged before filtering through the sintered-bed crucible.

Table II shows that in the concentration range of 43.5 to 347.8 mg. of selenium in 100 ml solution, the accuracy of the present method is $\pm 0.2\%$. The standard deviation is found to be $\pm 0.24\%$. The following anions do not interfere: fluoride, chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, sulphite, thiosulphate, thiocyanate, nitrate, nitrite, carbonate, phosphate, pyrophosphate, borate, molybdate, vanadate, arsenate, acetate, citrate, tartrate, oxalate, and cyanide. EDTA has no effect on the results of selenium estimation.

The present method is free from the interference by the following cations: Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺, Fe³⁺, Al³⁺, Cr³⁺, Mn²⁺, Bi³⁺, Sb³⁺, UO²⁺, Th⁴⁺, Ce³⁺, Pb²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, VO²⁺, Pt⁴⁺, Pd²⁺, Au³⁺, Sn²⁺, Sn⁴⁺, Ti³⁺, and Ti⁴⁺, Sn(II) and Ti(III) reduce Se(IV) to elementary selenium; but under the experimental conditions employed, the precipitation of selenium is not quantitative without the addition of amidinothiourea.

With amidinothiourea Cu(II), Hg(II), Ag(I), and Te(IV) furnish Cu(ATU)₂¹¹, HgS⁷, Ag³, and Te¹⁰ respectively. In presence of Te(IV), the results of selenium estimation are high. The interference of these ions can be removed by complexing the ions with citric acid. If Te(IV) is present, it should be oxidised to Te(VI) with K₂Cr₂O₇ before addition of the complexing agent. In case of Te(VI), molybdate and tartrate can also be used as masking agents. Separation of selenium from Cu(II), Ag(I), Hg(II), and Te(VI) and its subsequent

10. Nadkarni and Haldar, unpublished results.

11. Ray and Choudhary, *this Journal*, 1950, 27, 673.

determination with amidinothiourea have been achieved. Selenium was precipitated in presence of citric acid, filtered, and estimated, as described above. The filtrate was made ammoniacal and heated to boiling. On adding amidinothiourea to the hot solution, CuS , HgS or metallic Ag separated. CuS was filtered and dissolved in nitric acid and Cu(II) was estimated iodometrically. HgS and metallic Ag were filtered, washed, dried, and weighed as HgS and Ag respectively. When Te(VI) is present, the filtrate from selenium determination is heated to boiling and hydrazine hydrochloride and amidinothiourea are added. Elementary Te is precipitated and can be weighed after filtering, washing, and drying at 110° . The results of analysis of the following mixtures: (a) $\text{Se} + \text{Cu(II)}$, (b) $\text{Se} + \text{Hg(II)}$, (c) $\text{Se} + \text{Ag(I)}$, and (d) $\text{Se} + \text{Te(VI)}$ are summarised in Table III.

In conclusion it may be stated that the accuracy of the present method is fairly high and comparable to those of the standard methods for the estimation of selenium. It is quite rapid. Under the experimental conditions employed, anions and cations do not interfere.

Grateful thanks of the authors are due to the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, Government of India, New Delhi, for the award of a research training scholarship to one of them (R. A. N.) during the tenure of which this work was carried out.